

Recommendations for malaria prevention for personnel working in the
lowlands of Papua New Guinea

Abu S Galib

Diploma in Remote and Offshore Medicine

Module C10: Evidence and Research in Remote Medicine

The Royal College of Surgeons of Edinburgh

(Final: 24.03.2019)

Abstract

Malaria remains a serious endemic disease in Papua New Guinea (PNG) and recent trends are showing resurgence in the prevalence of this disease. The local population remains susceptible to malarial infections and carry the burden of morbidity and mortality in significant proportions. Also, foreign nationals, who are non-immune to the causative organisms, are at increased risk of manifesting severe forms of the disease. The Pinnacle Onshore Project (POP), will recruit both from the local population, and foreign nationals, and will operate in the lowlands of PNG, which are known to be endemic for malaria. It therefore becomes necessary, that all personnel become familiar with the current expert recommendations regarding the prevention of this disease.

Keywords: Malaria, prevention, WHO, Papua New Guinea, local, foreign.

Recommendations for malaria prevention for personnel working in the lowlands of Papua New Guinea

This report focuses on current trends in malaria prevalence in PNG, and provides recommendations for its prevention, based on expert opinions, specifically for the personnel who will work onsite, for the POP.

Resurgence of malaria in Papua New Guinea

PNG is witnessing a resurgence in the prevalence of malaria in recent times (“PNG’s nine-fold increase in malaria infections - Papua New Guinea,” n.d.). Information available on the World Health Organization website, shows that malaria infection rates remain high throughout PNG (“WHO | Country profiles,” n.d.). Infographics available in a more detailed report, “The Malaria Indicator Survey 2016-17”, pages 8, 40-41, shows that PNG is witnessing a resurgence in malaria prevalence throughout its lowlands (Hetzl et al., n.d.), (“Malaria Indicator Surveys - Access to Reports, MIS Datasets, Survey Information,” n.d.).

Risks for the local population

The local population, remains vulnerable to the infection and clinical manifestations of the disease. Special risk groups, such as pregnant women, infants, and children below 5 years of age, are affected the most (Lufele et al., 2017), (Hartman, Rogerson, & Fischer, 2010), (Laman et al., 2019). The morbidity and mortality in these risk groups remains a matter of grave concern. As such all local personnel must get acquainted with the current guidelines for prevention.

Risks for foreign nationals.

Foreign nationals, with no known previous exposure to malarial pathogens, are even more prone to develop serious and sometimes fatal manifestations of the disease (Loutan, 2003), (Pavli & Maltezou, 2010). Individuals moving in from another country often have either poor information or misconceptions regarding the risks of contracting malaria, and seriousness of the disease (“[What do Portuguese Travellers Know About Malaria? Pre-Travel Medicine Appointment Evaluation]. - PubMed - NCBI,” n.d.). There are numerous reports, regarding the incidence of imported malaria, from around the world (Angelo, Kozarsky, Ryan, Chen, & Sotir, 2017; Boreham & Relf, 1991; Kanayama et al., 2017). It is imperative that all foreign nationals who are planning to work in PNG, get acquainted with the expert recommendations regarding malaria prevention.

General precautions for both local population and foreign nationals. (“WHO | Information for travellers,” n.d.; “WHO | World malaria report 2018,” n.d.)

1. The prevention of mosquito bites, remains the first line of defense.
2. Use long lasting insecticidal nets (LLIN), while sleeping.
3. Wear full sleeve clothes, to prevent mosquito bites.
4. Use insect repellants, mosquito nets, coils, and aerosol sprays, to prevent being bitten by mosquitoes.
5. Avoid areas of high-density mosquito population, especially between dusk to dawn, for example swamps.

6. Remain alert regarding any potential breeding place of mosquitoes, around your working area, and promptly take action to drain any open stagnant water.
7. Practice good hygiene and access safe and potable water.
8. Try to contribute to the malaria vector control measures in your area. (“WHO | WHO publishes new guidelines for malaria vector control,” n.d.)
9. The guidelines available in this report, may have to changed, in the light of new information or recommendations, being available at a later date. It is advised, that all project personnel visit the clinic noticeboard at monthly intervals, to keep themselves updated.

Precautions for foreign nationals. (“WHO | Information for travellers,” n.d.)

1. If any individual who has not been to PNG before and have not stayed for extended periods of time, in this country, he or she has a high risk of getting infected by the malarial pathogens, and are at risk of developing severe clinical manifestations, which may even lead to death.
2. Malaria may have a delayed onset, so any occurrence of fever between 1 week to up to 3 months after arrival or leaving the endemic zone, should be promptly investigated.
3. Foreign nationals, will need to start chemoprophylaxis **BEFORE** entering PNG.

Recommended preventive treatment for the local population (“WHO | World malaria report 2018,” n.d.), (“Efficacy of artemether-lumefantrine and dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine for the treatment of uncomplicated malaria in Papua New Guinea. - PubMed - NCBI,” n.d.; Senn et al., 2012).

1. A visit to the primary care physician (PCP) is recommended to know if you are adhering to national guidelines for malaria control for PNG. Alternatively, please visit the site clinic.
2. If you do not belong to the special risk groups, as mentioned below, you should take medications as per the seasonal chemoprevention (SMC) therapy regimen.
3. Pregnant women and infants should take medications as per Intermittent preventive therapy (IPTp and IPTi respectively) regimen.
4. Children below 5 years should take medications as per seasonal chemoprevention (SMC) therapy regimen.
5. Recommended drugs:
Sulphadoxine+pyrimethamine(SP) for IPTp and IPTi, amodiaquine+SP(AQ+SP), for SMC.
6. No other drugs are currently recommended for prevention either due to widespread failure of prevention in PNG, or because of limited data available regarding efficacy and safety (Brabin et al., 2016; Dayananda, Achur, & Gowda, 2018).

Recommended preventive treatment for foreign nationals travelling into PNG (“WHO | Information for travellers,” n.d.)

1. A visit to your primary care physician (PCP) is essential to discuss the appropriate drug regimen.
2. No antimalarial drug gives complete protection.
3. Adherence to drug regimens, should be strictly complied with.

4. Foreign nationals, must continue preventive medications, even during break periods in their home country.
5. All drugs should be continued for 4 weeks, after permanently leaving the endemic zone.
6. There is also the possibility of late onset malaria.
7. Awareness of the adverse effects, of these drugs is vital. Anyone experiencing these adverse effects must follow further steps as recommended (item no. 9 and 10).
8. Recommended drugs for prophylaxis:
 - a. Mefloquine.
 - b. Atovaquone-proguanil combinations.
 - c. Doxycycline
 - d. Chloroquine is not recommended for prophylaxis due the presence of widespread resistance in PNG.
9. In case of neurological or psychological adverse effects, stop the drug immediately and consult the nearest PCP or the site clinic.
10. In case of persistent nausea, vomiting and diarrhea, do not discontinue medications, but visit the nearest PCP or the site clinic.

Recommendations for the project operators

1. Stock all recommended drugs in sufficient quantities.
2. Consult local authorities and procure nets, malaria prevention kits and ointments.
3. Beware of spurious drugs.

4. The project clinic will need malaria rapid diagnostic kits(mRDT) for the early detection of malaria at site.
5. A policy of shifting sick project personnel to well-equipped healthcare facility should be in place, and tested for practicality.
6. A program of vector control, will provide an additional safety net in the operating areas. (“WHO | WHO publishes new guidelines for malaria vector control,” n.d.)

References

- Angelo, K. M., Kozarsky, P. E., Ryan, E. T., Chen, L. H., & Sotir, M. J. (2017). What proportion of international travellers acquire a travel-related illness? A review of the literature. *Journal of Travel Medicine*, 24(5). <https://doi.org/10.1093/jtm/tax046>
- Boreham, R. E., & Relf, W. A. (1991). Imported malaria in Australia. *The Medical Journal of Australia*, 155(11–12), 754–757.
- Brabin, B. J., Ginny, M., Alpers, M., Brabin, L., Eggelte, T., & Kaay, H. J. V. D. (2016). Failure of chloroquine prophylaxis for falciparum malaria in pregnant women in Madang, Papua New Guinea. *Annals of Tropical Medicine & Parasitology*. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00034983.1990.11812428>
- Dayananda, K. K., Achur, R. N., & Gowda, D. C. (2018). Epidemiology, drug resistance, and pathophysiology of Plasmodium vivax malaria. *Journal of Vector Borne Diseases*, 55(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0972-9062.234620>
- Efficacy of artemether-lumefantrine and dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine for the treatment of uncomplicated malaria in Papua New Guinea. - PubMed - NCBI. (n.d.). Retrieved March 9, 2019, from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30290825>
- Hartman, T. K., Rogerson, S. J., & Fischer, P. R. (2010). The impact of maternal malaria on newborns. *Annals of Tropical Paediatrics*, 30(4), 271–282. <https://doi.org/10.1179/146532810X12858955921032>

- Hetzel, M. W., Saweri, O. P. M., Kuadima, J. J., Smith, I., Ura, Y., Tandrapah, A., ... Pulford, J. (n.d.). PAPUA NEW GUINEA MALARIA INDICATOR SURVEY 2016-2017: MALARIA PREVENTION, INFECTION, AND TREATMENT, 70.
- Kanayama, A., Arima, Y., Matsui, T., Kaku, K., Kinoshita, H., & Oishi, K. (2017). Epidemiology of Imported Malaria Cases in Japan, 2006-2014: A Sentinel Traveler Surveillance Approach. *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 97(5), 1532–1539. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.17-0171>
- Laman, M., Aipit, S., Bona, C., Aipit, J., Davis, T. M. E., & Manning, L. (2019). Contribution of Malaria to Inhospital Mortality in Papua New Guinean Children from a Malaria-Endemic Area: A Prospective Observational Study. *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.18-0769>
- Loutan, L. (2003). Malaria: still a threat to travellers. *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*, 21(2), 158–163.
- Lufele, E., Umbers, A., Ordi, J., Ome-Kaius, M., Wangnapi, R., Unger, H., ... Rogerson, S. (2017). Risk factors and pregnancy outcomes associated with placental malaria in a prospective cohort of Papua New Guinean women. *Malaria Journal*, 16(1), 427. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-017-2077-4>
- Malaria Indicator Surveys - Access to Reports, MIS Datasets, Survey Information. (n.d.). Retrieved March 20, 2019, from <http://www.malariasurveys.org/surveys.cfm?country=Papua%20New%20Guinea%202016-17#6085>

Pavli, A., & Maltezou, H. C. (2010). Malaria and travellers visiting friends and relatives. *Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 8(3), 161–168.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmaid.2010.01.003>

PNG's nine-fold increase in malaria infections - Papua New Guinea. (n.d.). Retrieved March 10, 2019, from <https://reliefweb.int/report/papua-new-guinea/png-s-nine-fold-increase-malaria-infections>

Senn, N., Rarau, P., Stanisic, D. I., Robinson, L., Barnadas, C., Manong, D., ... Mueller, I. (2012). Intermittent Preventive Treatment for Malaria in Papua New Guinean Infants Exposed to *Plasmodium falciparum* and *P. vivax*: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *PLOS Medicine*, 9(3), e1001195. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001195>

[What do Portuguese Travellers Know About Malaria? Pre-Travel Medicine Appointment Evaluation]. - PubMed - NCBI. (n.d.). Retrieved March 21, 2019, from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30684368>

WHO | Country profiles. (n.d.). Retrieved March 9, 2019, from <http://www.who.int/malaria/publications/country-profiles/en/>

WHO | Information for travellers. (n.d.). Retrieved March 9, 2019, from <http://www.who.int/malaria/travellers/en/>

WHO | WHO publishes new guidelines for malaria vector control. (n.d.). Retrieved March 9, 2019, from <http://www.who.int/malaria/news/2019/vector-control-guidelines/en/>

WHO | World malaria report 2018. (n.d.). Retrieved March 21, 2019, from <http://www.who.int/malaria/publications/world-malaria-report-2018/en/>

